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**PHONETIC, PHONOLOGICAL, AND MORPHOLOGICAL
CHALLENGES OF INTERMEDIATE ESL LEARNERS:
A CLASSROOM-BASED ANALYSIS**

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the phonetic, phonological, and morphological difficulties experienced by intermediate-level ESL learners in a classroom context. The study is based on a group of school students aged 12 to 14 studying at Registan Learning Center in Tashkent. The learners come from multilingual backgrounds, mainly Uzbek, Russian, and Azerbaijani, and study English to improve their language proficiency beyond the school curriculum. The article identifies five major linguistic challenges: pronunciation of dental fricatives, differentiation between short and long vowels, stress placement in multisyllabic words, irregular plural noun formation, and incorrect verb tense formation. Each problem is discussed in relation to learners' first language influence and teaching strategies designed to address these difficulties. The findings demonstrate the importance of targeted phonetic and morphological instruction in helping learners improve pronunciation accuracy and grammatical competence.*

Keywords: *ESL learners, phonetics, phonology, morphology, pronunciation, stress patterns, irregular plurals, verb tense formation, language teaching, intermediate learners.*

Аннотация. *Данная статья анализирует фонетические, фонологические и морфологические трудности, с которыми сталкиваются учащиеся среднего уровня ESL (английский как второй язык) в условиях учебного процесса. Исследование основано на группе школьников в возрасте от 12 до 14 лет,*

обучающихся в учебном центре Registan в Ташкенте. Учащиеся имеют многоязычный фон, в основном узбекский, русский и азербайджанский языки, и изучают английский язык для улучшения своих языковых навыков помимо

школьной программы. В статье выделены пять основных лингвистических трудностей: произношение межзубных фрикативных звуков, различение кратких и долгих гласных, постановка ударения в многосложных словах, образование неправильных форм множественного числа существительных и неправильное образование временных форм глаголов. Каждая проблема рассматривается с точки зрения влияния родного языка учащихся и методических подходов, направленных на преодоление этих трудностей. Результаты исследования показывают важность целенаправленного обучения фонетике и морфологии для улучшения точности произношения и грамматической компетенции учащихся.

***Ключевые слова:** учащиеся ESL, фонетика, фонология, морфология, произношение, модели ударения, неправильные формы множественного числа, образование временных форм глаголов, преподавание языка, учащиеся среднего уровня.*

Introduction: Teaching English as a second language requires understanding the linguistic difficulties learners face, especially when their native language structures differ significantly from English. This article focuses on a group of school students at Registan Learning Center in Tashkent, where I have been teaching for more than six months.

I have been teaching a group of school students at Registan Learning Center in Tashkent for more than 6 months. The group consists of 15 students, ranging in age from 12 to 14 years old whose English proficiency is at an intermediate level. The lessons last for 1 and a half hour including additional 1 hour practiced with an assistant. When it comes to the level of instruction, they are enrolled in a middle school ESL program, where they are given English lessons twice a week. The main reason why they take extra English classes after school is to improve their language skills beyond the lessons provided in their regular curriculum. According to the monthly progress tests, their IELTS scores are between 5.0 and 5.5 and at the CEFR rating scale B1 level. All of my students in the group have gained Basic English instruction at school from their earlier grades like elementary grammar and basic vocabulary. Regarding the primary topic and objectives of my class, we are currently focusing on more advanced grammar usage, gradual improvement of integrated language skills, and communicative competencies. The students in my group have come from different linguistic backgrounds and their primary languages are Uzbek, Russian or even

Azerbaijani. Being bilingual and multilingual, their native and second language usage in everyday settings has reflected a wide range of linguistic structures and phonetic systems. The language of instruction is mainly in English and Russian. Aside from that, their exposure to English also varies significantly. Some of them use the language actively through interacting with peers and native speakers, surrounding themselves with the language, and, of course, with the media. However, other students have limited practical use of English outside the classroom. The student's level of motivation also varies very widely: most of them are inspired by becoming a fluent language user and exploring English-speaking countries, while others' primary aim is to take a language certificate and study at prestigious universities. Over the past six months, we have covered a variety of materials with the students. The first three months were devoted to Round-Up 3, Student Book 3rd Edition by Virginia Evans and Jenny Dooley. This well organized book has clear sections and exercises that guide students through grammar, vocabulary, and language skills. Following this, we focused intensively on improving students' speaking skills for one month. I found Let's Talk Level 1 Student's Book with Digital Pack by Leo Jones to be the most suitable option for my students. This book has significantly enhanced their speaking abilities through practical conversations and using the language in real-life settings. Since the fifth month, I have been conducting lessons using Solutions, Intermediate: Student's Book 3rd Edition by Tim Falla and Paul A Davies. This book mainly focuses on enhancing students' integrated skills and broadening their worldview at the same time.

Methodology. This classroom-based analysis focuses on five specific linguistic difficulties observed among intermediate ESL learners.

The first challenge is the pronunciation of dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/. The pronunciation of dental fricatives are particularly challenging for my students since they are Russian-speaking learners of English. The main reason is that dental fricatives do not exist in Russian and as a result, learners often replace them with sounds, such as /s/ and /z/ for /θ/ and /ð/. —There is a natural tendency for geographically distant accents to become more different, simply because speakers who live far away have not tended to communicate with one another historically, so their ways of speaking drift apart (McMahon, 2020, p. 5). My lessons last for one and a half hour and I am going to dedicate about 20 minutes to explaining them how to pronounce these sounds correctly. First of all, I will use some visuals and videos to show how the tongue should be positioned between teeth to produce dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/. After that I will make them practice these sounds with drills, repetitions and phonetic exercises. Students can also check whether they are pronouncing them correctly or not through recording themselves and comparing their pronunciation to native speakers.

The second challenge involves the pronunciation of short and long vowels. A week ago I noticed one error made by my intermediate level students. This error is connected with the pronunciation of short and long vowels. For example, they pronounce both words —ship and —sheep with the same vowel sounds and length. However, /ɪ/ in "ship" is a short vowel, whereas /i:/ in "sheep" is a long vowel and the words should be pronounced according to this rule. When I asked them about the reason why they pronounce these words in a similar way, I was responded that in Russian, vowel length is not so important as it is in English. Yavas (2016) noted that —length differences in vowels or consonants may be used to make lexical distinctions in languages (p.23). It is obvious from the author's statement that correct pronunciation of short and long vowels is essential to distinguish words from each other since length differences may result in complete change of a word's meaning. For that reason, I decided to separate 30 minutes from my lesson and provide them mainly with listening exercises and audio recordings to differentiate between short and long vowels. This can be done with digital bingo tools where I will call out both short and long vowel sounds and students will correspond them to the sounds on their cards.

The third challenge is incorrect stress placement in multisyllabic words. My intermediate level students also struggle with not being able to put correct stress in multisyllabic words because of differences between Russian and English stress patterns. An example of this case can be the word interesting which has nearly the same translation into Russian —интересный where the stress is on the third syllable. In the word interesting the first syllable should be stressed, however Russian speakers might incorrectly place the stress on other syllables, such as /ɪn.tə.'res.tɪŋ/ or /ɪn'tres.tɪŋ/. According to Payne (2011), —The stress patterns of English are described in any good introduction to English phonetics, phonology, or pronunciation. Even grammatical particles like pronouns, auxiliaries, and prepositions can take stress if they are being contrasted with something else (p.82). From this statement we can conclude that English has fixed stress patterns in many words, including multisyllabic ones. Russian stress, however, is more flexible and is less tied to specific word syllables. One of the most effective ways to teach them correct stress placement in multisyllabic words is though making them familiarize common stress patterns. For example, in English the stress of words shifts depending on their parts of speech, whether a word used as a noun, verb or adjective like in words REcord (noun) or. reCORD (verb). As a home assignment, they will listen to various media such as news and podcasts to imitate their stress patterns.

The fourth challenge concerns irregular plural nouns. My students have some problems with forming the plural of irregular English nouns because of the lack of irregular plural nouns in their native language which is Russian. They are used to saying mans or sheeps instead of men and sheep respectively. In Russian, nouns ending in a consonant generally form their plural by adding the suffix -ы or -и. My students apply this rule by unconsciously adding the suffix -s at the end of each word to make them plural. However, they always forget about irregular nouns that do not follow the standard rule of adding -s or es. "When plurals begin to appear regularly, the child forms them according to the most general rule of English plural formation. At this point, the child's overgeneralization of the rule results in words such as 'mans,' 'foots,' or 'feets' (Moskowitz, 1978, p. 100).|| To help my students with irregular plural nouns in English, first of all, I am going to provide clear explanation of the topic during 15 minutes. 10 minutes will be spent on practice exercises like quizzes and matching games that makes the process of memorizing irregular plurals both effortless and engaging.

The fifth challenge is incorrect verb tense formation, particularly with irregular past tense verbs. My intermediate level students make some mistakes in the formation of verbs in past tense, even though I have covered this topic twice. In Russian grammar, verbs are not divided into regular and irregular past forms like in English. They form the verbs in past tense just by adding several suffixes at the end of words and there is no need to remember a list of irregular verbs for them. Common errors mainly include saying dranked instead of drank or using teached instead of taught, because of not fully learning the past forms of irregular verbs. They make these mistakes unconsciously when they are involved in speaking activities, however, in completing grammar exercises, they have some time to think about the correct answer relying on theoretical explanations. To overcome this issue, I am going to spend 30 minutes focusing only on explaining the formation of verbs in past tense and practicing them with the means of flashcards. After that I will assign from 10 to 15 verbs as vocabulary homework in which they need to remember irregular verbs creating visual aids and using their mnemonic devices. According to Payne, —The past tense forms could not be predicted based on any patterns that apply to other verbs—they simply have to be memorized as distinct words.|| From this statement it is clear that for regular verbs we can predict the past tense form adding —ed|| to the base form. However, many irregular verbs do not follow this standard rule and learners need to memorize the past form of each irregular verb.

Conclusion. The analysis of these intermediate ESL learners demonstrates that first language influence plays a major role in phonetic, phonological, and

morphological errors in English. The pronunciation of unfamiliar sounds, vowel length distinctions, stress placement, irregular plural formation, and irregular verb tense formation present significant challenges for learners from Russian-speaking and multilingual backgrounds. However, through focused instruction, practical exercises, listening activities, and memorization techniques, these difficulties can be reduced. Effective teaching strategies that directly target these linguistic areas can significantly improve learners' pronunciation accuracy and grammatical competence, contributing to their overall communicative development in English.

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